

Mobility Ratios of Clay-membrane Electrodes in Aqueous and Aquo-organic Solvents

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Membranes, which are good for their electrochemical performance, have been utilised for the determination of the mobility ratios, viz., U_K/U_{Na} , U_K/U_{NH_4} , U_{NH_4}/U_{Na} , from the measurements of E.M.F. of cells constituted of the membranes separating two solutions having known activities of Na and K ions, K and NH_4 ions, and NH_4 and Na ions in aqueous and aquo-organic solvents. These are found to vary with the nature of the membranes, i.e. on their method of preparation, with the activity range of the cations, and with the nature of the solvent medium. It is, however, observed that the values of the mobility ratios can be easily reproduced in the same activity ranges. The values of U_K/U_{Na} and U_K/U_{NH_4} in aquo-ethanolic solutions are greater than those in aqueous solutions and increase with the increasing percentage of ethanol in the solution, whereas U_{NH_4}/U_{Na} decreases under the same conditions. U_K/U_{Na} is almost the same in aquo-glycol solutions as in aqueous solutions.

Use of clay-membrane electrodes for measurements of cation activities in aqueous solutions has been emphasised by Marshall¹, Bose², Adhikari³, and Chatterjee⁶. According to Marshall it has been found expedient to consider the clay membrane as a cationic reversible electrode. If such a membrane separates two solutions having different cationic activities, the E. M. F. observed should be equal to that given by the Nernst equation, provided that the membrane is perfectly reversible. Working with a large number of electrodes, it has been found by these workers that a correspondence, such as one mentioned above, is usually obtained in moderately dilute solutions. Marshall considered the two surfaces of a clay membrane as the seat of exchange of cations. The exchange equilibrium between the ions on the surface of the membrane and those in the solution determines the characteristics like 'mobility ratios' or the 'differential heats of adsorption on the membrane'. Experience has shown that when a mixture of two cations is present, the effect of one can be expressed in terms of the other by means of 'mobility ratios'⁶. The concept arose from the original picture of ion transport through the membrane³. Since the clay membranes are considered to be non-porous by Marshall, the idea of 'mobility ratio' is not strictly applicable here. For these special types of electrodes, he proposed what he termed 'differential heat of adsorption'. If the membranes are supposed to act like the metal-metal ion electrodes within the validity range of the Nernst equation, the mobility ratio, as suggested by Mitra⁴ and Bose², becomes related to the difference between the "standard" electrode potentials of the two electrode surfaces exchanging the two cations concerned by means of the equation:

$$E_{AB}^{\circ} = (RT/F) \ln U_A/U_B,$$

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, **43**, 1155; 1948, **52**, 1284.
2. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, **3**, 5, 109.
3. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 817.
4. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1953, **1**, 12.
5. Meyers and Sievers, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1938, **19**, 649, 665, 689.
6. *This Journal, Ind. & News Ed.*, 1949, **12**, 73.

where E_{AB}^0 is the difference in standard electrode potential for the cation pair $A^+ - B^+$. Any of these quantities, which are characteristics of the membrane electrode for the particular ion pair, can, however, be utilised to calculate cationic activity in mixtures. The present communication is primarily concerned with the evaluation of the mobility ratios for selected pairs of cations from amongst Na, K, and NH_4 in aqueous and aquo-organic solvents since these membranes are found to be satisfactory for cation-activity measurements in aquo-organic solvents⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedures were similar to those reported earlier⁵. The membranes found satisfactory by the previous procedures^{5,7} were used for determination of 'mobility ratios' of different cation pairs in different solutions. For determination of Na/K mobility ratios, for instance, solutions of known Na^+ and K^+ ion activities were placed on two sides of the membrane. From the observed E.M.F., the mobility ratio for the ion-pair concerned was calculated according to the equation:

$$E = (RT/F) \ln (\alpha_K / \alpha_{Na}) (U_K / U_{Na}) + (RT/F) \ln [a_{Cl} - (K^+)] / [a_{Cl} - (Na^+)]$$

for the cell arrangement :

The mobility ratios, U_K / U_{Na} , U_K / U_{NH_4} , and U_{NH_4} / U_{Na} , in aqueous solutions and in water-ethanol and water-glycol solutions, calculated in the same way, are recorded in Tables I-IV.

TABLE I

Membrano.	Inside $K^+0.003$ Outside $Na^+0.0029$		Inside $K^+0.009$ Outside $Na^+0.00887$		Inside $K^+0.027$ Outside $Na^+0.0263$		Inside $K^+0.081$ Outside $Na^+0.0283$	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$
A. In aqueous solutions.								
Podegaon:								
Ca-form	14.5 mv	1.65	20.8 mv	2.11	26.2 mv	2.50	25.4 mv	2.56
Na-form	20.6	2.10	26.2	2.60	34.1	3.52	35.0	3.80
H-form	12.6	1.53	18.2	1.90	26.2	2.62	28.2	2.86
	(0.8)*		(0.8)*		(0.85)*		(0.6)*	
B. In 25% ethanol + 75% water solutions.								
	Inside $K^+0.0087$ Outside $Na^+0.0005$		Inside $K^+0.0258$ Outside $Na^+0.0251$		Inside $K^+0.0741$ Outside $Na^+0.724$			
Podegaon:								
Ca-form	23.7mv	2.37	26.1	2.56			40.0	4.53
Na-form	29.9	3.00	35.0	3.62			50.0	6.65
H-form	23.7	2.37	27.5	2.70			43.1	5.10
	(0.8)*		(1.0)*				(0.65)*	

7. This *Journal*, 1963, 48, 373.

8. Cf. Table IV, "Electrochemical Data", Elsevier Publishing Co. 1952, pp. 166, 172,

TABLE I (contd.)

C. In 75% ethanol + 25% water solutions.

Padegaon:	Inside K ⁺ 0.00265		Inside K ⁺ 0.00732		Inside K ⁺ 0.0191	
	Outside Na ⁺ 0.00258		Outside Na ⁺ 0.00711		Outside Na ⁺ 0.0186	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$
Ca-form	23.1 mv	2.35	32.3 mv	3.41	36.0 mv	3.85
Na-form	30.4	3.14	38.6	4.30	42.5	5.00
H-form	22.2	2.28	32.7	3.40	36.8	3.95
	(0.5)*		(0.7)*		(0.6)*	

* Figures in parenthesis refer to less E.M.F. for Cl⁻/Cl⁻ in Tables I-III.

TABLE II

Membrane.	A. In aqueous solutions.				B. In 25% ethanol + 75% water solutions.			
	Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.000037		Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0065		Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.000943		Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.00817	
	Outside Na ⁺ 0.00007		Outside Na ⁺ 0.00877		Outside Na ⁺ 0.00096		Outside Na ⁺ 0.00848	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$
Padegaon:								
Ca-form	24.5 mv	3.420	22.4 mv	2.42	20.4 mv	2.26	21.5 mv	2.32
Na-form	30.5	3.200	25.2	2.02	24.8	2.07	27.5	2.80
H-form	26.5	3.281	19.0	2.10	16.5	1.04	14.8	1.80
	(nil)*		(0.8)*		(nil)*		(0.8)*	

C. In 75% ethanol + 25% water solutions.

Padegaon:	Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.000777		Inside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0034	
	Outside Na ⁺ 0.001914		Outside Na ⁺ 0.00713	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_{NH_4}}{U_{Na}}$
Ca-form	14.5	1.83	12.4	1.78
Na-form	22.2	2.48	20.2	2.39
H-form	11.0	1.64	11.9	1.72
	(nil)*		(0.7)*	

TABLE III

Membrane.	Inside K ⁺ 0.009		Inside K ⁺ 0.001		Inside K ⁺ 0.00872		Inside K ⁺ 0.000998	
	Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0085		Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.000957		Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0081		Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.00943	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$
Padegaon:								
Ca-form	2.0 mv	1.02	6.0 mv	1.15	6.0 mv	1.20	4.2mv	1.04
Na-form	2.5	1.04	5.5	1.10	5.5	1.17	4.2	1.04
H-form	2.5	1.04	5.5	1.10	5.5	1.17	4.2	1.04
	(nil)*		(1.6)*		(nil)*			

C. In 75% EtOH + 25% water solutions.

Padegaon:	Inside K ⁺ 0.0073		Inside K ⁺ 0.00093	
	Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0063		Outside NH ₄ ⁺ 0.0008	
	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	$\frac{U_K}{U_{NH_4}}$
Ca-form	16.8mv	1.87	21.5mv	2.10
Na-form	16.8	1.67	22.0	2.18
H-form	16.0	1.62	22.0	2.18
	(nil)*		(0.8)*	

* Figures in parenthesis refer to less E.M.F. for Cl⁻/Cl⁻

TABLE IV

In 20% glycol + 80% water soln.

Membrane.	Inside K ⁺ 0.00208 Outside Na ⁺ 0.00285			Inside K ⁺ 0.00893 Outside Na ⁺ 0.0087		
	Obs. E.M.F.	Less E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$	Obs. E.M.F.	Less E.M.F. for Cl ⁻ /Cl ⁻ .	$\frac{U_K}{U_{Na}}$
Padegaon						
Ca-form	13.0	0.0	1.53	20.3	0.6	2.10
Na-form	16.2	"	1.74	25.7	"	2.55
H-form	13.0	"	1.53	25.6	"	2.10

DISCUSSION

The calculation of mobility ratio has been done with different types of membrane electrodes, described earlier^{3,7} and working in the range of activities in which the membrane electrodes perform well. The mobility ratio is supposed to be a characteristic quantity for a particular membrane electrode, but it has been found to vary, often widely, with the activity of the ions concerned². The mobility ratio of the electrodes, prepared from the same clay material, appears to depend to a certain extent on the nature of the cation (Ca²⁺, NH₄⁺, H⁺) originally saturating the clay, as is evident from the tables. Even with the clays saturated with the same cation, the mobility ratio shows variations with the change of the solvent. It is to be seen that U_K/U_{Na} and U_K/U_{NH_4} values increase in aquo-organic solvents compared to those observed in aqueous medium, just as these do in ethanol-water mixtures having a high percentage of ethanol. U_{NH_4}/U_{Na} decreases gradually with increase in the percentage of ethanol. In glycol-water, the U_K/U_{Na} values remain almost constant as in water itself. Other ion pairs have not yet been studied with this solvent mixture. The cause for this change in mobility ratio with change in solvent is yet to be explained; it may possibly be due to change of ionic conductance with the change in dielectric constant of the medium. For instance, the cation transference numbers of NaCl in 0.0% methanol and 50% methanol are 0.3963 and 0.4437 respectively at infinite dilution⁸.

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